

Training Manual 3

Fish Health and Management in Aquaculture Systems

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Introduction

Fish health management is a key part of modern aquaculture and forms the foundation for sustainable, productive, and profitable fish farming. As global demand for fish protein rises, aquaculture systems serve as an essential sources of food and livelihood. To meet this demand, farmers must therefore give priority to the health and welfare of fish. Healthy fish support efficient growth, stable yields, and reduced losses, all of which are critical for successful operations. Aquaculture is carried out through various production systems including earthen ponds, cage culture, recirculating aquaculture systems, each with its own management needs and operational dynamics. Despite these differences, all systems rely on effective fish health management to function optimally. Consistent attention to fish health is therefore crucial to protect aquatic ecosystems and ensure long-term viability of the aquaculture industry.

At the end of this module, the men and women participants will,

- Explain the key factors that influence the occurrence of fish diseases in aquaculture
- Recognize common behavioral and physical symptoms that indicate fish disease
- Demonstrate knowledge of effective prevention and control measures in aquaculture.

Module Timing, Location, and Materials required

No	Session	Estimated time	Location
1.	Major Disease and Health Management Factors in Aquaculture Systems	2 hrs	Living Lab 2, Kajjansi
2.	Basic Diagnosis of Fish Diseases and Related Symptoms	2hrs	
3	Disease Control Strategies in Aquaculture Systems	2hrs	

Flip charts, manila papers, markers, pens, pencils,

Session 1: Major Disease and Health Management in Aquaculture Systems

Interactive Activity 1: Individual Reflection

Take 5–7 minutes to quietly reflect on your own fish farming experience (or what you know about fish farming in your area). On a piece of paper, write short answers to the following questions:

- What common fish health problems or diseases have you seen or heard about?
- What do you think caused these problems? (e.g., water quality, feed, overcrowding, parasites, etc.)

Facilitator's Notes

What causes diseases in aquaculture system?

Three main factors namely: the environment, fish (host), and disease agents contribute to ill-health within aquaculture systems. Understanding these factors and how they interact with each other is essential for developing effective disease prevention and health management strategies. Figure 1 presents the factors that can influence disease occurrence.

Figure 1: Factors influencing occurrence of diseases on fish farms (Moreira, Márcio & Schrama, Denise & Farinha, Ana & Cerqueira, Marco & Raposo de Magalhães, Cláudia & Carrilho, Raquel & Rodrigues, Pedro. (2021). Fish Pathology Research and Diagnosis in Aquaculture of Farmed Fish; a Proteomics Perspective. *Animals*. 11. 125)

Environmental Factors and Their Influence on Fish Disease

Environmental factors play a major role in the development and spread of diseases in aquaculture systems. Even in the presence of healthy fish and absence of aggressive pathogens, a poorly managed environment can trigger disease outbreaks. Conversely, maintaining optimal environmental conditions can help prevent diseases and support fish health. The following are key environmental tenets that significantly influence disease occurrence in aquaculture. Poor farm hygiene contributes significantly to disease outbreaks in aquaculture systems. When fishponds or tanks are not regularly cleaned, organic matter such as uneaten feed, feces, and dead fish accumulates. This waste becomes a breeding ground for harmful microorganisms including bacteria and parasites, increasing the

risk of infection and compromising fish health. Slow water currents result in stagnant conditions that hinder the proper distribution of oxygen and the removal of waste products. In such environments, toxic substances like ammonia can build up quickly, stressing the fish and encouraging the growth of disease-causing organisms. Good water circulation is therefore essential to maintain water quality and support fish wellbeing. Poor water quality is one of the most critical environmental stressors in aquaculture. Parameters like temperature, pH, oxygen levels, and the presence of harmful substances must be kept within optimal ranges. When water quality declines, fish become stressed and more susceptible to diseases due to weakened immune responses, making regular water monitoring and management a priority. The location of a fish farm influences its exposure to pollutants and pathogens. Farms sited near industrial zones, agricultural runoff areas, or other farms face higher risks of contamination and disease spread. Strategic site selection and proper environmental assessments are therefore vital to minimize exposure to external disease sources. Contact with wild fauna poses an ongoing risk to biosecurity in fish farms.

One critical factor is the age or life stage of the fish. Young fish, such as larvae and juveniles, often have immature immune systems, making them more vulnerable to infections. As fish grow older, their immunity may improve, but they may still face age-related vulnerabilities depending on the species.

Stress exposure plays a major role in weakening a fish's natural defenses. Stress can arise from a range of conditions including poor handling, overcrowding, transportation, sudden temperature shifts, or inadequate oxygen levels. When fish are stressed, their immune response is suppressed, increasing their risk of infection even in the presence of relatively low pathogen loads. Susceptibility also varies among fish due to genetic and species-specific factors. Some fish are inherently more prone to certain pathogens, especially if they are selectively bred for traits other than disease resistance. Additionally, fish that have a history of illness or come from weakened genetic lines may be less capable of fighting off

new infections. The strength of the immune system is a key determinant in disease resistance. A fish with a weak or compromised immune system whether due to malnutrition, stress, or chronic health issues is far less capable of fending off pathogens. Ensuring proper nutrition, reducing stressors, and maintaining healthy genetic stock are essential steps in supporting a robust immune system in aquaculture setting.

Pathogen as components of the disease triangle

Pathogens are organisms that cause disease in fish and other aquatic life. These include bacteria, viruses, fungi, and parasites and each type of pathogen behaves differently in aquaculture environments. The diversity among pathogens means they differ significantly in their ability to cause harm (virulence), how well they adapt to new environments, and how easily they spread among fish populations. These differences directly affect the frequency and severity of disease outbreaks in aquaculture systems. Pathogen outbreaks are treated with which when used frequent or inappropriately can lead to the emergence of resistant strains. These resistant pathogens are more difficult to treat and control, posing a major challenge in aquaculture. Virulent strains of pathogens are another critical factor of concern. Some pathogens naturally possess higher virulence and therefore cause more severe disease or spread more aggressively among fish populations. The presence of such strains can lead to rapid outbreaks with high mortality rates, especially in densely stocked or stressed fish environments. The lack of effective diagnostic tools further contributes to delayed identification and treatment of diseases. In many cases, by the time a pathogen is detected, the infection may have already spread significantly. Lastly, the existence of asymptomatic carriers presents a hidden risk in disease transmission. Some fish may carry and shed pathogens without showing visible signs of illness, silently introducing infections into otherwise healthy populations. These carriers can complicate control efforts and highlight the need for regular health monitoring and biosecurity protocols.

What causes fish diseases?

Sources of disease agents include the culture water in which the fish is growing, but they can also be transferred to the aquatic environment from elsewhere. The latter include farm workers, farm tools such as fish nets, and contaminated water run-off from human settlements, crop gardens, livestock farms, slaughter and processing plants, as well as other industries. The external fish surfaces, including skin, gills, and fins, are in direct contact with water that may carry pathogens such as bacteria, viruses, fungi, and parasites. Additionally, fish possess a relatively delicate immune system compared to terrestrial animals, making them more susceptible to infections, especially under stressful conditions like poor water quality, overcrowding, or nutritional deficiencies. These biological and environmental interactions make fish highly vulnerable to disease outbreaks in both natural and cultured systems.

Some factors lead to fish being easily affected by diseases. Such factors include overcrowding (high stocking density), poor water quality, and erratic feeding practices. The latter may result in starvation of the fish or residual feed that lead to water quality deterioration. Intrusion by predators may introduce diseases since they are at times carriers or act as intermediate hosts for fish parasites. Pond overfertilization, usually with cattle or poultry faecal matter that may carry disease agents, but also leads to algal bloom and reduced dissolved oxygen. The algal bloom appears as green/red/brown discoloration of the water.

Sudden, explosive die-off (usually with no prior signs of ill-health) involving all fish present usually indicates the presence of an acute environmental problem. This may be due to lack of oxygen, the presence of toxic chemicals, or high temperatures. In case of poor water quality, fish usually exhibit signs such as gasping for air, dead fish with open mouth and opercula, massive fish kills or deaths. Fish deaths that follow the appearance of a few sick fish, unusual behaviour, or loss of appetite are often associated with the early stages of infectious diseases. Diseases may arise after fish handling, due to the infliction of wounds and stress.

Session 2: Basic Diagnosis of Fish Diseases and Related Symptoms

Interactive Activity 2: Group Exercise

- Set up printed pictures or short descriptions of diseased fish. Pin these pictures on the walls around the living lab. Divide participants into small groups (3–5 people each). Participants are requested to walk in the living lab and at picture note and discuss:
 - What symptoms do you see?
 - What might be the cause/problem?
 - What first action should be taken?
- Share some of the answers to the questions in a plenary

Facilitator Notes:

Fish, like all living creatures, can become sick. For smallholder farmers, early detection of diseases is very important because if problems are not noticed quickly, diseases can spread fast and cause serious losses. Fish often show signs of illness through their appearance and also their behavior. Learning to recognize these basic symptoms helps farmers take the right action early. By closely observing the fish, one can see signs of ill-health, which can occur before death. Fish can exhibit various signs of disease or illness, which can be categorized into behavioral and physical symptoms. Sick fish may stop eating or eat excessively and produce trailing faeces. They may swim weakly, lazily, or erratically, and some may float belly up. Fish might also rub themselves against hard surfaces, a sign of irritation or itching, and may crowd near water inlets. The fish can stay away from others, swim at the surface or along the sides of the tank or move sluggishly, hang at an angle under the water surface and may exhibit gasping for air or opening

the mouth. Other abnormal behaviours include darting, moving in circles/ twisting and, loss of equilibrium. Fish diseases can be caused by many factors and these show up in physical ways that farmers can see with their own eyes. For example, a sick fish may develop spots, wounds, swollen areas, or changes in skin and fin color. Sometimes the gills or eyes may also look abnormal. Physically, signs include gaping mouths, open sores, lesions, bloated bellies, or loss of scales. The gills may appear pale, eroded, swollen, bloody, or discolored. Fins may deteriorate, fold abnormally, or stay clamped against the body. Cloudy or bulging eyes, skin discoloration, abnormal body shape or posture, and the presence of parasites or injuries are also common signs of disease. Growths/protrusions, swellings, wounds, bloody areas may be seen on the internal and external body surfaces. The eyes may appear opaque, blood-tinged, swollen, sunken or popping out. Some signs associated with various diseases include skin ulcers, nodules on the skin, and gills; swollen or distended abdomen; bloody patches (hemorrhages) on the skin, gills, gill cover and base of the fins. In some cases, white cottony growths can be seen on the skin, gills, eyes, and other body surfaces. These physical signs are important clues because they tell us that the fish is under stress or being attacked by disease organisms. By learning to recognize these outward symptoms early, farmers can act quickly to reduce losses and protect the rest of the stock (see figure 2)

Figure 1: Impacts of human activities and their feedback mechanisms

Point to Ponder: What kind of symptoms can you observe from the images in figure 2 above?

Interactive Activity 3: Guided Tour

- Divide participants into small groups (4–6 people). Lead groups to different tanks/ponds one by one. At each stop, ask groups to:
 - Look closely at the fish – What physical signs can you see? (skin, fins, gills, eyes, body shape)
 - Observe behavior – How are the fish moving? Are they feeding? Are they coming to the surface?
 - Consider environment – Is the water clear or dirty? Any unusual smell? Groups write down their observations before moving to the next station.
- In a plenary each group shares one physical and one behavioral sign they observed.

Session 3: Disease Control Strategies in Aquaculture Systems

Interactive Activity 4: Peer to Peer Exercise

- Form pairs with the person next to you. Each of you will take turns sharing your experiences. You will have 3 minutes to talk about a fish disease problem you have experienced or heard about.
 - What you did (or would do) to control or prevent it. What worked well and the challenges you faced.
 - After the first person finishes, switch roles so that the second person also has 3 minutes to share their story.

In fish farming, the challenge of disease management lies not just in identifying illness, but in the very

Practices that prevent the entry of disease agents, and close monitoring for sick fish should be done daily. Maintaining good water quality, hygienic conditions of the farm and offering good quality feeds nutrition enhance the ability of fish to fight infections. Maintaining a hygienic fish farm environment is the best preventive method checking disease outbreaks. There should be foot or tyre baths at the entrance for the persons and the vehicles accessing the farm, appliances/tools/ equipment should be kept clean and disinfected. Obtain fish stock from certified breeders and avoid direct introduction into the rearing ponds (quarantine) fish stock since they can be infected or disease carriers, a source of diseases. Minimize stress and handling of the fish.

As soon as signs of ill-health are observed, some water and sick fish should be collected and submitted for further analyses. The second step is to record the water quality parameters. Thirdly, flush in fresh water (remove some water and add more) to destabilize the unfavorable parameters, then measure again to see improvement in the water quality. In case of infectious illnesses, changing and adding fresh water reduces

the pathogen load. Fourthly, review and analyse the water quality records for the previous 1 – 2 months, then evaluate the trends and levels over time before any further intervention. Fifthly, if the water quality parameters are acceptable, then contact a fish health professional.

Predators are an issue in case of pond system of aquaculture production system. Prevent predators from accessing the farm by regular clearing of the farm site as predators hide in the bush, fence off the pond site, and protect from flood water. Keep pond well aerated to prevent disease outbreak

In fish farming, the challenge of disease management lies not just in identifying illness, but in the very nature of aquatic pathogens and the biology of fish. Unlike terrestrial livestock, fish rarely show early signs of illness due to their schooling behavior and the difficulty of individual observation. By the time symptoms are noticeable, the disease is often widespread and difficult to treat effectively. Many common pathogens have no known cure once an infection sets in. Furthermore, treatment in water-based systems is complex, costly, and can lead to environmental degradation or drug resistance if mismanaged. This reality makes prevention far more practical and sustainable than treatment. By focusing on environmental control, good management practices, and biosecurity, fish farmers can reduce stressors and limit exposure to harmful organisms. The following preventive strategies can be adopted for they not only protect fish health but also improve overall productivity and profitability in aquaculture systems.

- Proper pond regulation enhances the fish's living environment and helps reduce the risk of disease. Essential practices include trimming pond vegetation to limit pest and predator habitats and disinfecting ponds before stocking to eliminate harmful organisms. These steps lead to better fish yields and a lower risk of disease outbreaks.
- Daily management should be assigned to a responsible person to ensure consistency. Key tasks include stocking, feeding, fertilizing, and monitoring water quality. Adopting the 'four fix' feeding method can improve feed efficiency and reduce disease risk. Inspecting the

pond regularly, especially after rainfall, helps detect and correct problems early. Removing weeds, cleaning feeding platforms, and handling fish gently during transfer or transportation are also essential for maintaining fish health.

- Before introducing fingerlings into a new pond, disinfect them to prevent the introduction of pathogens. Use salt or chemical baths, applied in containers like pails or net cages, to reduce bacterial or parasitic loads and ensure healthy stocking.
- To disinfect fish as they feed, suspend bamboo baskets with bleaching powder or bags containing copper sulphate and ferrous sulphate in feeding areas. These agents help control bacterial and parasitic infections. Regular replacement and proper placement are necessary for their effectiveness.
- Contaminated equipment or feed can quickly spread disease. Always use clean, fresh feed. Wash snails and soak aquatic plants in diluted bleach before feeding. Mix bleach with manure before applying it in the pond to ensure safe decomposition. Clean tools after every use using sunlight exposure or disinfectants like copper sulphate.
- Apply chemical treatments periodically to maintain pond health. Use copper sulphate, or bleaching powder to control parasites and bacteria. Quicklime can be applied to improve poor water conditions. Always ensure even distribution of solutions for maximum effectiveness.
- Prevent diseases like enteritis by using garlic-mixed feeds, especially during high-risk seasons. Adding salt improves absorption and enhances the antimicrobial effect. Feed can be administered as paste on grass or in pellet form, depending on the species preference.
- To prevent the spread of diseases due to fish movement, establish a quarantine system. Quarantine new or sick fish before introducing them to healthy populations and restrict the transport of diseased fish. Monitoring inter-regional movement helps control disease transmission and protects overall stock health.

Summary

Disease outbreaks in fish farming are largely shaped by the interaction of three core factors: the environment, the host (fish), and pathogens (disease agents). Poor water quality, unhygienic farm management, overcrowding, stress, and the presence of disease-causing organisms are identified as the leading contributors to fish ill-health. Environmental mismanagement such as pond over-fertilization, stagnant water, poor aeration, and pollution from surrounding human activities or farms further increase vulnerability to diseases. Fish themselves are susceptible at certain life stages, especially when young or stressed by poor handling, inadequate nutrition, or high stocking densities. Their relatively delicate immune systems make them more prone to infections. Diagnosis of fish disease relies heavily on recognizing both behavioral symptoms and physical symptoms. Prevention is emphasized as the most effective and sustainable strategy, since fish often show late symptoms and treatments can be costly, environmentally harmful, and ineffective once diseases are advanced. Key preventive measures include strict farm hygiene, maintaining water quality, using clean equipment, sourcing fingerlings from certified breeders, quarantining new stock, reducing stress, controlling predators, and adopting regular monitoring. Biosecurity measures like disinfecting equipment, regulating pond conditions, careful feeding, and restricting movement of fish are strongly encouraged. Ultimately, integrating sound management practices not only reduces disease risk but also enhances productivity and profitability in aquaculture systems.

Module Key Messages

- Fish diseases often become noticeable only when already widespread, making treatment costly, less effective, and sometimes environmentally damaging. Preventive measures such as maintaining water quality, practicing farm hygiene, minimizing stress, and quarantining new stock are the most reliable and sustainable ways to protect fish health and reduce losses.
- Even in the absence of aggressive pathogens, poor farm practices such as overcrowding, over-fertilization, dirty ponds, and stagnant water create conditions that stress fish and trigger outbreaks. Good management of the environment (cleaning ponds, aeration, regulating stocking density, using quality feeds) is critical in minimizing disease occurrence and supporting healthy fish growth.
- Recognizing behavioral and physical symptoms of ill-health early, coupled with strong biosecurity measures, helps farmers take timely action before diseases spread. Simple steps such as disinfecting tools, restricting predator access, using certified seed, and carefully monitoring fish behavior are powerful tools for preventing devastating losses and ensuring long-term aquaculture profitability.

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